

Magnetic Bioactive Materials for Bone Regeneration and Tissue Engineering

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Tissue Engineering is an interdisciplinary area that combines the concept of cell biology, drug delivery, materials science and engineering, which focused on the regeneration of specific cells and functional tissues. Depending on the scaffold materials cell growth or tissue regeneration can be efficient; cells can undergo attachment, growth, differentiation and proliferation on effective bioactive materials. Biomaterials like bioactive glass (45S5, 1393, 1393B3, 1393B1, 58S), ceramic materials (hydroxyapatite), glass-ceramics, biodegradable or biocompatible polymers are specially used for the preparation of such kind of scaffolds [1, 2]. Based on the nature of the used bioactive materials different processes and technologies are used for scaffold preparations, e.g. freeze casting, solvent casting, robocasting, foam replication method, 3D printing, electrospinning etc.

Bioactive glasses, especially 45S5, 1393, 1393B1, have been considered as a promising alternative in the treatment of bone related diseases, therapeutic ions (B, Cu, Zn, Mg, Co, Sr, Ca) doped glass scaffolds also have the ability to form bone minerals, like hydroxycarbonated apatite (HCA), after immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF). Mesoporous glass based materials prepared by sol-gel method are excellent materials with high specific surface area, and possess very high loading capacity for successful delivery of potential growth factors (proteins, enzymes, drugs etc.). Recent results indicate that magnetic field may stimulate the new tissue generation by enhancing the cell proliferation and differentiation process [3]. Magnetic fields were also found to be beneficial for promoting bone regeneration, integration of bone and implants, and increase of bone density [4]. For this purpose, magnetic force based tissue engineering has been reported that utilizes magnetic nanodevices (magnetic cationic liposomes, magnetic gelatine nanoparticles, magnetic nanoparticles loaded hydroxyapatite-collagen etc.) to yield magneto-responsive features to the cells [5].

However, a possibility that has rarely been considered is the application of magnetic nanoparticles in tissue regeneration, is their incorporation into scaffolds. The aim of this study is to combine the concept of biomaterials, especially bioactive glasses, and polymer materials with magnetic nanotechnology for efficient hard and soft tissue regeneration. For successful tissue regeneration some crucial factors should be maintained, such as the use of suitable non-toxic and biocompatible materials for scaffold preparation, culture medium, temperature and most important, cell numbers in scaffolds. The last factor is quite difficult to manage properly; magnetic force guided cell seeding can be applied to optimise the cell numbers in scaffolds. High cell number with sufficient packing of cells at the interior of the scaffold has been addressed by loading the cells with magnetic nanoparticles (magnetic cationic liposomes or chitosan-coated magnetic nanoparticles), hydrating the scaffold with the suspension of the cells and applying a magnetic field consequently [6]. Such kind of protocol can be productive for cell seeding into the deeper sites of the 3D porous scaffolds, which may not be possible in absence of external magnetic field. Thus, the magnetic field intensity has been found to have positive influence on the depth of the cell seeding into the scaffold [7]. After all mechanical stimuli similar to those experienced *in-vivo* by cells, couldn't provided to the seeded cells at the time of incubation on scaffold. Moreover, direct magnetic actuation can provide mechanical stimuli experienced by cells *in-vivo*, which can't be simulated by *in-vitro* tests in incubators. These are

achieved through attachment of magnetic nanoparticles on specific ionic channels present on the cellular membrane, acting as stress generators [8]. It was demonstrated that mechanical stimulation of primary human osteoblast cells by attached magnetic nanoparticles promoted the regeneration of bone matrix under the influence of external magnetic field [9].

Finally, our work relies on magnetic nanoparticles with therapeutic ions (Zn, B, and Ca) doped mesoporous glass-polymer fibre composites. Citrate stabilized superparamagnetic magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles will be prepared by co-precipitation method [10]. Therapeutic ions doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGN) will also be prepared separately by sol-gel method [11]. These will be used for preparation of biocomposites. Poly-vinylpyrrolidone (PVP; a water soluble polymer) will be dissolved in water. Required amount of magnetic nanoparticles and mesoporous glass nanoparticles will be added to the polymeric solution and the whole mixture will be homogenized by ultrasonication. The PVP/ Fe_3O_4 /MBGN sol will be used for fibre drawing by electrospinning. Due to the presence of citrate groups at the surface the magnetite nanoparticles can be easily dispersed in aqueous polymeric solution. The presence of polymeric chains in the aqueous medium will also partly or completely eliminate interparticle attractive forces, thus preventing their aggregation.

Morphology of the final fibre mats will be studied by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Transmission electron microscope (TEM) is also be useful to study the distribution of MBGN (~150-180 nm) and magnetite nanoparticles (~ 10-20 nm) in fibres due to their different size range, and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDAX) for elemental distribution in the fibre. Magnetic properties of the fibres will be measured by a magnetometer at room temperature and finally the cell culture study will be done with different cell lines in cell culture medium (*in-vitro*). Based upon the results of the *in vitro* analysis, *in vivo* studies will be envisaged on selected fibre mats. The final objective is to evaluate the bioactivity of the magnetic bioglass-polymer fibre composites after implantation in the animal body.

Keywords: Tissue regeneration, Cell, Scaffold, Biomaterials, Magnetic Nanoparticles.

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